

References and acknowledgements for ERAU 2024 Discovery Day presentation
GPT-4 Assisted Categorization and Visualization of NTSB UAV Accident Reports

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Acknowledgements

The author extends heartfelt thanks for the exceptional support and guidance received from the COMPASS Research Mentoring Program at Embry-Riddle Aeronautical University.

Special recognition is given to Dr. Emily Faulconer for her continuous and profoundly insightful feedback.